

THE IMPACT OF KARATE TRAINING ON THE PHYSICAL AND MENTAL HEALTH OF SCHOOL-AGE CHILDREN (ON THE EXAMPLE OF CONTACT KARATE IN GEORGIA)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15024985>

Abstract

Karate is one of the most widespread and popular Japanese martial arts worldwide. It is considered a system of physical defense or fighting skills, consisting mainly of striking techniques. Its name refers to the emphasis on techniques that do not require weapons. Traditional karate, as practiced today, is an art, a sport, and a proven method of self-defense. It is practiced by over 130 million enthusiasts worldwide. The Georgian history of karate began in 1967.

According to numerous foreign literature, karate is more than a martial art. It is a discipline that instills valuable life skills in all people, including children and contributes to their overall development. In addition to the physical aspects of training, karate brings other benefits to children's mental and social well-being. The health benefits of martial arts are numerous. In addition, karate is not just movements - it is a philosophy. It instills values such as perseverance, respect, and discipline. Karate training offers numerous benefits for the physical, mental, and social development of children. In addition to physical training and self-defense skills, children gain valuable life skills such as self-discipline, focus, respect, and teamwork. Karate instills self-confidence, promotes emotional balance, and provides a positive outlet for stress. There are also a lot of studies that have examined the effects of karate on physical and brain development and function.

Used by most of the authors the recognized and widely used the Eurofit Physical Fitness Test Battery and the Total Motor Development Test (TGMD-2) to study the impact of karate on children's physical health appear unknown to our country. Thus we surveyed it through specially developed questionnaires and interviews, in which the children themselves and their parents were involved. In total 88 children and their parents were interviewed. The results of our study confirm the significant positive impact of karate training on the physical health and mental development of school-age children. Based on our research, several recommendations were composed.

Keywords: Contact karate, children's training, physical and mental development.

Introduction

Karate is a martial art that is said to have originated in the Ryukyu Islands, now Okinawa, Japan. As interest in karate grew, masters moved to Europe and America to popularize the art. Karate became even more popular in the West in the 1960s with the release of martial arts films.

It is one of the most widespread and popular Japanese martial arts. It is considered a system of physical defense or fighting skills, consisting mainly of striking techniques. Its name refers to the emphasis on techniques that do not require weapons. In Japanese, karate is known as *heiwa no bu*, 'the martial art of peace', and is practiced by over 130 million enthusiasts worldwide.

Traditional karate, as practiced today, is an art, a sport, and a proven method of self-defense.

'Karate is not a game. It is not a sport. It is not a system of self-defense. Karate is half physical training and half spiritual. A karateka who has devoted the necessary years to training and meditation is a calm person. He is not afraid. He can remain calm even in a burning building' [Masutatsu Oyama, Quote].

The Georgian history of karate began in 1967. At that time, there was not a single karate specialist nor full-fledged literature, but a group of enthusiasts laid the foundation for the development of karate. The government persecuted everyone passionate about this oriental combat sport. A similar situation existed in other republics of the Soviet Union. But by 1979, the number of people practicing this sport had grown so much that the government was forced to recognize karate as a

sport. Georgian karateka already had ten years of training experience and were prepared for this. Their successful performances in tournaments and championships of various ranks began.

The Georgian Karate Federation was founded in 1980, and the first Georgian Championship was held in the same year. Karate was banned, and its teaching was declared a criminal offense in 1983, by the USSR Council of Ministers decree.

During the collapse of the Soviet Union in the late 80s, after karate was legalized again, the second stage of karate development began in Georgia. In 1989, the opportunity arose to establish contacts with foreign specialists and invite them. Famous Japanese karateka came to Georgia: Kanazawa, Higaona, Suzuki, Nanbu, Ikata, Hishataka, Kasuya, etc. The result was not long in coming - Georgian athletes achieved notable success on the international stage [Georgian Sports].

Currently, many karate organizations operate in Georgia: the Georgian National Shotokan Federation, the Georgian National Sports Karate Federation, the Georgian National Contact Karate Federation, the Georgian Karate Federation, the Tbilisi Karate Federation, the Karate Federation, etc.

According to numerous foreign literature, karate is more than a martial art. It is a discipline that instills valuable life skills in all people, including children and contributes to their overall development. In addition to the physical aspects of training, karate brings other benefits to children's mental and social well-being. The

health benefits of martial arts are numerous. In addition, karate is not just movements - it is a philosophy. It instills values such as perseverance, respect, and discipline. These values form the foundation of life and guide a person's choices and actions. Karate is a discipline that instills valuable life skills in children of all ages and promotes their overall development.

Karate training offers numerous benefits for children's physical, mental, and social development. In addition to physical training and self-defense skills, children gain valuable life skills such as self-discipline, focus, respect, and teamwork. Karate instills self-confidence, promotes emotional balance, and provides a positive outlet for stress. Moreover, the social interaction and friendships formed in the dojo contribute to the overall well-being of children. Karate enables them to develop holistically and equips them with the skills necessary for a successful future [Emplify, Empowering Achievement].

The benefits of karate in children have been studied by Turkish researchers (Gazi University, Turkey). This study investigated the effect of a 10-week karate training program on motor skills development in 5-7 year-old children. A total of 28 participants were included in the study: 18 in the karate group and 10 in the control group. The karate group was exposed to a fundamental karate training program (*kihon*), consisting of 90-minute sessions four days a week for ten weeks, in addition to physical education classes at their schools. In contrast, the control group did not participate in any sports activities except for physical education classes at their schools. Data were collected using the Eurofit test battery and the TGMD-2 test. When comparing the pre-test anthropometric measurements of the karate group with the control group - no significant differences were observed.

In contrast, significant differences were obtained in height, body mass index, and body fat percentage. In the post-test analysis of the two independent groups, there were statistically significant differences in favor of the karate group regarding height and body fat percentage ($p < 0.005$). In the pre-post-test analysis of the Eurofit test and TGMD-2, all parameters for the karate group showed statistically significant improvements ($p < 0.001$), while the control group showed no statistical difference. After comparing the karate and control groups, the post-test results of the Eurofit test and TGMD-2 showed significantly higher scores (statistically significant differences) in all parameters for the karate group. In conclusion, the study showed that a 10-week karate training program had a positive effect on the motor development of the participating children [Yasin Arslan, Belma Yavaşoglu, et al., 2024].

There are a lot of studies that have examined the effects of karate and other forms of martial arts on brain development and function. Karate and other forms of martial arts require significant training and the mastery of complex movements. These types of movements have been shown to improve cognitive abilities such as attention, memory, and learning. Research has also shown that martial arts training can lead to neural plasticity, which refers to the brain's ability to adapt and change over time. Neural plasticity is essential for the development and functioning of cognitive processes.

Exercise and other forms of physical activity have been shown to have beneficial effects on both cognitive performance and overall brain health. In addition, incorporating mindfulness practices into martial arts training improves stress management. Research suggests that karate and other forms of martial arts have the potential to enhance cognitive performance, particularly in the areas of executive function and attention. That may also impact people who already have cognitive impairments or who are at risk for cognitive decline. The findings also indicate that training in karate and other forms of martial arts can benefit a person's overall physical and mental well-being. The findings also indicate that training in karate and other forms of martial arts can benefit a person's overall physical and mental well-being [Venkateswar Pujari, 2022].

An interesting study has been published using virtual reality technology to study changes in mental health and cognitive function levels in karate athletes. It is known that the use of virtual reality technology in sports generally is increasing. This study concluded that virtual reality-based physical activity improves the mental health and cognitive function of karate athletes [Ferry Fendrian, Amung Ma'mun, Yudy Hendrayana et al., 2024].

As we have seen, most authors used the recognized and widely used Eurofit Physical Fitness Test Battery and Total Motor Development Test (TGMD-2) to study the impact of karate on children's physical health. To study the influence on children's mental development, various testing methods, including the use of virtual reality technology, were used.

Unfortunately, the abovementioned tests and their methodology appear unknown to our country.

Based on the above, it became necessary to conduct our research by collecting subjective data - by studying data available on the Internet about existing Georgian karate organizations and clubs and through specially developed questionnaires and interviews, in which the children themselves and their parents were involved.

The study was conducted by surveying the current situation in the clubs affiliated with the Georgian Contact (Shinkyokushinkai) National Karate Federation (President Avtandil Shengelia). Among them: Kokai (Tbilisi), Spaeri (Tbilisi), Shin (Tbilisi), Mebrzoli (Tbilisi), Gorgasali (Telavi) and Champions Academy (Adjara).

88 children and their parents were interviewed using the developed questionnaire. Among them, by club: 18 children in the Champions Academy; 16 children in Spare; 15 children in Kokai; 9 children in Gorgasali; 11 children in Mebrzoli, and 19 children in Shin.

The age of the children surveyed ranges from 6 to 17 years. Among the respondents, 57 are boys (64.7%), and 32 are girls (35.3%).

Among the motivations for starting karate training, 5 children (5.6%) mention bullying, 17 (19.3%) - media (movies, advertising), 31 (35.2%) - friends, 36 (40.9%) - parents.

The duration of karate training varies from 2 months to 11 years.

The frequency and duration of training is mostly three times a week, with each training session lasting 1-1.5 hours.

65 children (73.8%) are happy with the coach, 23 (26.2%) are moderately satisfied, and none of the respondents expressed dissatisfaction.

Of the external effects of exercise, 25 children (28.4%) reported improved concentration and learning abilities, 61 children (69.3%) reported improved self-defense abilities and 47 children (53.4%) reported improved behavior (discipline).

Conclusion

The results of our study are interesting and confirm the significant positive impact of karate training on the physical health and mental development of school-age children.

The study found that children start practicing karate as early as 6. In addition, the number of girls is 35.3%, which is quite a high figure for this type of sport. Among the motivations for starting karate training, 72% indicate friends and parents. Only 19.3% mention the media (movies, advertising), which is low and suggests the need to strengthen activities in advertising. The comfortable training situation in the clubs and the qualifications of the coaches confirmed that 73.8% of children were happy with the training, and none of the respondents expressed dissatisfaction.

The respondents' answers on the external effects of training on physical and mental development were significant. 28.4% of children noted concentration and learning improvement, 69.3% improved self-defense skills, and 53.4% improved behavior (discipline). These data indicate the positive impact of karate on children's physical and mental development.

The results of our research on the physical and mental development of children coincide with the results of studies conducted by foreign researchers. Our research is indeed largely subjective, since instead of the Eurofit Physical Fitness Test Battery and the Total Motor Development Test (TGMD-2), which are generally accepted abroad, and provide objective and reliable data, we used a survey method, which is less accurate and objective. However, we believe that this research has great prospects and needs to be continued in the conditions of the introduction and use of the abovementioned tests.

Based on our research, the following recommendations composed:

1. To inform the general population, including school-age children and adolescents, as well as their parents, about the positive impact of contact karate on physical and mental development, karate organizations and clubs operating in Georgia should create appropriate websites, which, along with achievements in this sport, will provide the history of karate, its spread

throughout the world, and its benefits for the physical health and mental development of the younger generation.

2. To study and monitor the physical and mental development of school-age children and adolescents, the Eurofit Physical Fitness Test Battery or the Total Motor Development Test (TGMD-2), which is widely accepted abroad, should be introduced in Georgia, which provides objective and reliable data on physical development. In addition, the education and healthcare sectors should be involved in this process.

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